

THE STEREOTYPE OF WOMAN AS SEXUAL OBJECT IN TARA MOSS'S *HIT*

Dr. Patil H. B.

Associate Professor

A. C. S. College,
Palus

Abstract-

Tara Moss is a post-modern Canadian-Australian author of crime fiction. She was born in 1973 in Canada. Later, she migrated to Australia. She is now citizen of both Canada and Australia. Her novels explore the crime as the most prominent aspect of post-modern world.

Key Words: *Sexual Harassment, Sexual Pleasure, Morally Debauched People, Gone Astray Generation*

Tara Moss's other novels include *FETISH* (2000), *SPLIT* (2002), *COVET* (2004), and *SIREN* (2009). In her fictional world, she explores the crime and its motives in some way or other. Her novels gain great critical attention as exploration of post-modern world. Many themes and aspects like post-modern generation, changed lifestyle, changed concept of crime etc. can be attributed to the novel *HIT*.

The present paper is an attempt to interpret and analyse the stereotype of woman as sexual object in HIT. The focus is on the ill-treatment to the woman in the world of men. Stereotype can be defined as something repeated without variation. It is something confirming to a fixed or general pattern. These patterns mark the standardised mental picture held in common by society. Stereotype is a fix idea or image that many people have of a particular type of person or thing. Stereotype of post-modern woman presented in this novel based on social, cultural and mental generalizations. These women characters exemplify the object of men's sexual desire, who are treated as objects only, without having any emotions, who fulfill the lust of men.

The story of the novel is about Damian Cavanagh, son of Jack Cavanagh, who is very rich businessman in the Australia and his friend Simon Aston. They are involved in the

murder of two girls. Damian Cavanagh is gone astray Youngman, who is too much lusty and interested in underage Asian girls brought from poor families of Thailand and Philippines. Damian is thirty years old youngster, who does not have any kind of interest in his father's business. He is involved in night parties, clubs, liquor, pubs and underage girls. He is well known as a great tipper in the club-dancing girls. All these services are provided to Damian by his friend Simon Aston, who is parasite on the Cavanagh family.

Once in the party, Damian Cavanagh attempts a sexual intercourse with an underaged Asian girl of thirteen or fourteen. The girl drinks from a plain water bottle, which contained not water but the colorless and odorless psychoactive substance G.H.B. or gamma-hydroxybutyrate, otherwise known as Grievous Bodily Harm, the latest drug Simon has introduced Damian to. When Damian returns after bath and finds the girl unconscious and with no perceptible heartbeat. She becomes dead.

The poor Asian countries like Thailand and Philippines have a lot of poor families. Underaged girls in those families are taken to Australia as sex workers. Sadly, some parents sell their girls for getting money. These girls are brought to Australia and provided to fulfill the sexual desires of men. The speciality of these Asian girls is that they do not complain against men during sexual intercourse. They accept the treatment given to them by the people like Damian Cavanagh. Damian is too much obsessed by the attraction of underaged Asian girls.

Damian stands before the dead underaged Asian girl, which is recorded in the mobile by Meaghan Wallace, who is invited in the party by her employer. She is twenty-three, who is already quite familiar with the desires of men, and she has no illusions about Groobelaar's intentions. Groobelaar is her employer and interested in Meaghan Wallace. He continuously tries to push her towards having an affair with him but Meaghan doesn't respond him.

The description of the dead Asian girl is given as,

'A naked girl lay prone on an unmade bed, the young face, chin buried in a pillow, the dark eyes wide open, staring lifelessly, her mouth gaping in an awful silent scream, the fingers outstretched as if the girl had been reaching for the doorknob in her final breath. From the bedroom the musty scent of sex mixed with a horrible, sickly sweet odour Meaghan had not

encountered before. Dark glossy hair of her fanned out around her head as she lay stomach down, back and buttocks fully exposed.

‘ The famous man Damien Cavanagh stood at the foot of the bed arguing animatedly with the other man, neither of them bothering to attempt to revive the girl or cover her nakedness. The girl’s body looked so small and vulnerable in death, her limbs splayed out.’ (Hit-11)

Here in this incident, we can see and understand that a woman is considered as an object of sexual desire of men. Men do not think of her morally, it is a mental image of men fixed from their childhood. Their ideology is formed by the social circumstances to treat woman as an object of lust. Damien is thirty years old and has sexual intercourse with the girl of fourteen or thirteen. See the age difference. The lusty men do not think of warrants emotions. It is a cruel act. which does not think of morality.

Simon Aston, who is close friend of rich Damien Cavanagh, is involved to provide girls to Damien. Simon Aston has sexual relations with many girls, who are from Asia or some are maids in his residence. Both of them have lasty attitude towards the woman in general. They do not think of marriage and family, but only to enjoy and utilize women with power of money.

Damien has Estee as a maid in his house, who is a new maid, liteh, pale, beautiful with cascading locks of raven hair tied in a loose ponytail at her nape. Estelle is gorgeous and friends is actually French, probably to try to appear more cultured. Cavanaghs go through a maid once or twice a year it seemed. Damien drives the ugly ones away, and messed with the pretty ones. Simon Aston wonders if Damien has the pretty ones. Simon Aston wonders if Damien has fucked her already or not. It is a stereotype of woman in the minds of men as a sexual object.

Women feel uncomforted, when Damien and Simon look at them. An engagement means nothing to Damien, as he has been engaged for the past six months to Carolyn, a pretty but boring young woman of whom his parents approved. The engagement has not even slightly dampened his nocturnal activates. When Damien sees any girl or women, he desires in mind sex withe them,

Night Parties, clubs, Pubs are the aspects of the post postmodern period. Too many people usually visit these places, where they can get pleasure especially sexual pleasure. Men

spend too much money by giving tips, by having sex with dancing models. Girls take the job as a dancer in the club to earn more money. They know men spend much money to get sexual pleasure. It is demand of the men to have dancers in the club. Meagan Wallace is a stripper in the club where she gets the money. With the help of the extra money, girls in the dance bar fulfill their materialistic demands. It is a projection of woman as an object of pleasure.

Lee Lintan is a pimp for Asian sex workers. Simon Aston frequently has contacted him to bring girls over for Damien's special parties, and he always has a fresh batch of pretty faces Damien has liked Lee's Asian girls because they are pettier and pretty and they don't speak English or question anything. There is none of the 'I' do this, but I don't do that or the you can touch me here, but not there, that they would get with the Australian girls. These girls never complain, even when Damien leaves them with burns, bruises or whip marks and lee can get them young.

When the protagonist and private investigator Marked wander wall goes to Melbourne, where dead Meaghaan Wallace's friend A my camillery works in the club of Mr. Larry moon, she observes that the owner Mr. Moon is making a lot of more money by using girls as dancers in his club. Mahedde also observes around the Mr. Moon's house stone carvings of female hudes set into water features against the fence. The stained glass detail pictured hued women variously reclining over one another or dancing through pendulous breasts free to the wind. When marketed visits Mr. Larry Moon, he says hi, beautiful, continuing to undress her with his eyes. He is obsessed with nudes not particularly well executed once, either. There is a big bronze sculpture of a nude on the hall table next to the stairs.

Everyone in the Australia knows Damien is one of the richest heirs in Australia .He would buy girls the best champagne there is and he gives the most amazing tips, especially to the little Asian girls. Everyone knows he loves Asian. He uses to have these wild parties and invite some of the girls over. He is free with the tips.... lots of tips for everyone in the party and clubs.

The girls brought from Asia are forced as sex slaves or migrant sex workers. It seems cruel and un just to force anyone to have to service over 500 men before free of the debt contracts that has brought them into the country.

Generally men use insulting and slang words or language while reforming to woman
e.g.

Simon wondered when he saw private investigator make vanderwall, 'Well why the fuck is she here? This is just what I bloody need, some nosy bitch snooping around.'

another example on next page

Simon Aston's story was that his friend Damien Cavanagh has developed a preference for petite Asian girls young ones and for nearly a year Simon has procured girls for his friend's pleasures. These girls are in enough demand that they are constantly being trafficked from poorer countries like Thailand and the Philippines, where they would either be coerced into sexual slavery or would happily accept the prospect of prostitution in order to make the money they and their families desperately need. Some of them are even sold by their own parents, such was the desperation in their villages.

The particular girl at the party is given champagne and cocaine after sex, when Damien has got up to shower, Simon believes she has drunk from a plain water bottle which has contained not water but the colourless and odourless psychoactive substance. GHB or gamma-hydroxybutyrate, otherwise known as Grievous Bodily Harm the latest drug Simon has introduced Damien to when Makedde Vanderwall visits Mr. Larry Mon's house, he becomes irritated by her interest to meet Amy Comilleri, who works in his club. 'He says, "What the hell is a girl like you doing working as a private dick? (dick: slang for penis) Larry asked with a tone of incredulity, changing the subject completely. "You seem like a smart girl. Why waste your time sniffing around like a dog in other people's affairs, when you could make some good cash using the body God gave you? Why don't you come work for me? You have got the goods.'" (Hit 332)

Reference:

Moss, Tara. Hit. Australia: HarperCollins, 2006.